

EVALUATION OF MINERAL AND NUTRITIVE COMPOSITION OF UNRIPE *MUSA PARADISIACA L.* (PLANTAIN) FRUIT

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Abstract:

*In order to increase the awareness of the importance of some African staples, unripe plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*), an important dietary staple in Benin City, Nigeria was investigated for its nutritional and mineral compositions. Results obtained from the proximate nutritional analysis revealed that mature unripe plantain purchased from Uselu market in Benin City, Nigeria contained 60.22% moisture, 0.86% ash, 5.54% fat, 20.84% crude fibre, 5.05% protein and 7.49% carbohydrate. Also, results obtained from the mineral analysis using atomic absorption spectroscopic method revealed that the fruit contained 2754 mg/100g iron, 1360 mg/100g potassium, 320.1 mg/100g zinc, 282 mg/100g calcium, 180.6 mg/100g copper, 130 mg/100g magnesium, 65.9 mg/100g manganese and 26.1 mg/100g sodium. The substrate was found to contain significantly high amount of Iron when compared with results from other workers. Other tested heavy metal minerals like chromium, lead and cadmium were absent.*

Keywords: *plantain, proximate, mineral, nutritional, evaluation*

1.0.INTRODUCTION

Plantain (*Musa paradisiaca L.*) is a nutritious food with many health benefits. It is a good source of energy and a major food staple in West, Central and Sub-Saharan Africa. It is noteworthy that over 2.11 million metric tons of the fruit are produced annually in Nigeria (Akinsanmi et al., 2015). When compared with banana, plantain is taller in height, firmer and has lower sugar content (Folayan and Bifarin, 2011). Different parts of plantain have been used for different domestic and medicinal purposes. The fruit is eaten as food, the juice extract from the leaf is used in the treatment of fresh wounds and cuts while its sap is used as a remedy for epilepsy, diarrhea and dysentery

(Gill, 1992). Foods made from plantain fruit in Nigeria have different names based on how they were prepared. They include “Bole” (roasted plantain fruit), “Dodo” (fried ripe plantain fruit), “Kpekere” (thin sliced fried plantain fruit - unripe), and “Amala” (dried plantain flour prepared with hot water, to be swallowed with soups). Plantain contains flavonoids and polyphenols which are natural beneficial compounds found in plants. They act as antioxidants and help in fighting free radicals which cause oxidative stress in the body. It is also noteworthy that plantain helps in regulating hormones associated with obesity and reduces the chances of obesity (Sarah and Osama, 2020).

Adequate nutritional analysis of food materials is the basis for understanding, developing and implementing effective food intervention programmes to improve human nutrition (Elmadfa and Meyer, 2010). Therefore, it is of great necessity to take into consideration and evaluate the mineral and nutritive composition of plantain fruit as an important staple in Nigeria. This research work is aimed at providing information on the nutritional and mineral composition of a mature plantain fruit from Benin City, Nigeria and also to increase awareness of its nutritional potentials and health benefits.

2.0. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

A bunch of mature freshly harvested *Musa paradisiaca L.* (Plantain) fruit was obtained from Uselu Market, Benin City, Nigeria. The fruits were washed with distilled water, air-dried and their peels removed. Their pulps were sliced with a sharp clean knife to about 6 to 10 mm and were used for the analysis.

Determination of Percentage Moisture Content

Five (5) g of the sample was weighed into a crucible of known weight and placed in an oven at 105°C for 2 hr. The weight of the sample and the crucible was noted and continuously monitored until a constant weight was obtained. Loss in weight was calculated as the percentage moisture content according to the expression in equation 2 below (Moronkola *et al.*, 2011).

$$\% \text{ Moisture} = \frac{\text{Loss in weight due to dryness}}{\text{Weight of sample taken}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$= \frac{W_2 - W_3}{W_2 - W_1} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where; W_1 = weight of empty crucible,
 W_2 = weight of crucible + sample before drying and
 W_3 = weight of crucible + sample after attaining constant weight on drying

Determination of Percentage Ash Content

A porcelain crucible with lid was ignited in a hot Bunsen burner flame and transferred into desiccator to cool and the crucible was weighed. Five (5) g of the sample was accurately weighed into the crucible and gently placed in the muffle furnace at 600°C for 4 hr. The crucible was placed in the desiccator to cool. The ashed sample in the crucible was weighed after cooling. The ash content was calculated using the formula in equation 3 below (Moronkola *et al.*, 2011).

$$\% \text{ Ash content} = \frac{W_3 - W_1}{W_2 - W_1} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Where, W_1 = weight of empty crucible,
 W_2 = weight of crucible + sample before ashing and
 W_3 = weight of crucible + sample after ashing

Determination of Percentage Crude Protein Content

Five (5) gram of finely dried sample was weighed on ashless filter paper. The paper with sample was folded and dropped into the digestion flask. Twenty (20) ml of sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) and 4 pieces of granulated zinc were added and then heated gently inside a fume cupboard for 6 hr. The content in the flask was allowed to cool. The solution was diluted with distilled water and transferred into 800 ml Kjeldahl flask. 100 ml of 40% NaOH was added and distilled. This was followed by

titration against 0.05% of boric acid solution using methyl red as indicator. The protein content was estimated from the amount of nitrogen present in the sample according to equations 4 and 5 (AOAC, 1990).

$$\% N = \frac{0.014 \times M \times V \times 100 \times D.F}{\text{Weight of Sample}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

$$\% \text{ Crude Protein} = \% N \times 6.25 \quad (5)$$

Where M = the molarity of acid, V = the volume of acid used, and D.F = the volume ratio of solution.

Determination of Percentage Crude Fat

Two (2) gram of the sample was transferred into a beaker and weighed; the weight was noted as “W”. Thereafter, 10 ml of water was added, and the solid was dispersed by agitation. Ten (10) ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added and immersed in a boiling water bath until the solid particle dissolved and the mixture become brown in colour. This was allowed to cool and 10 ml of ethanol was added and agitated vigorously. A dried clean flask was weighed and recorded as “W1” and the ether layer was transferred into the flask and placed in a boiling water bath to evaporate the ether. The extraction was repeated by adding 50 ml diethyl ether in order to evaporate the ether leaving the fat behind. The fat and the flask was weighed and recorded as “W2”, and then the fat content was calculated as a percentage as shown in equation 6 below (Moronkola *et al.*, 2011).

$$\% \text{ Fat} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

Where, W = weight of the sample,
W1 = weight of dried flask and
W2 = weight of dried flask fat residue.

Determination of Crude Fibre

Five (5) grams of the sample and 200 ml of 1.25% H₂SO₄ were heated for 30 min in a beaker and filtered. The residue was washed with distilled water until it was acid-free. Two hundred (200) ml of 1.25% NaOH was used to boil the residue for 30 min after which it was filtered and washed with distilled water until it was alkaline-free. It was then rinsed once with 10% HCl and twice with ethanol. Finally it was rinsed with petroleum ether three times. The residue was put in a crucible and dried at 105°C in an oven overnight. After cooling in a desiccator, it was ignited in a muffle furnace at 550°C for 90 min, to obtain the weight of the ash (AOAC, 1990).

Determination of Total Carbohydrate

To determine the crude carbohydrate content of a sample, the percentages of the remaining constituents were summed up and subtracted from 100%. The value obtained from this, gives the crude carbohydrate content of the sample (Moronkola *et al.*, 2011).

$$\text{Carbohydrate \%} = 100 - (\text{moisture \%} + \text{protein \%} + \text{ash \%} + \text{lipid \%} + \text{crude fiber \%}). \quad (7)$$

Mineral Analysis

The mineral analysis was done using standard methods as described by Horwitz, 2000. These methods use atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) as described by the Association of Analytical Communities (AOAC). The minerals that were assessed were Fe, K, Zn, Ca, Cu, Mg, Mn and Na. Heavy metals such as Cr, Pb and Cd were also assessed.

Apparatus:

A 250 ml digestion tube, heater, funnels, 25 ml volumetric flask, filter papers, and beakers

Reagents:

Nitric – perchloric acid digestion mixture (ratio 2:1), nitric acid – water mixture (ratio 1:1), hydrochloric acid – nitric acid mixture (ratio 3:1), and nitric-perchloric-sulphuric acid (ratio 5:2:1).

3.0. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Nutritional/Proximate Analysis of Plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*) Fruit

% Moisture	% Ash	% Fat	% Crude Fibre	% Protein	% Carbohydrate
60.22±0.16	0.86±0.13	5.54±0.20	20.84±0.19	5.05±0.24	7.49±0.21

Mean ± Standard deviation of three replications

Results from Table 1 show that aside from high moisture content of plantain fruit, it also contains high fibre and carbohydrate contents. Dietary fibre helps in lowering cholesterol in the body and also helps in reducing the risk of developing heart disease, diabetes, and

constipation. It also helps in reducing the risk of developing colon cancer as it properly regulates human bowel movement (Surampudi *et al.*, 2016). Averagely high carbohydrate content of the substrate is also essential as it qualifies it as a healthy diet.

Table 2: Mineral Composition of Plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*) Fruit

S/N	Mineral	Composition (mg/100g)
1	Iron (Fe)	2754.0±0.25
2	Potassium (K)	1360.0±0.20
3	Zinc (Zn)	320.1±0.21
4	Calcium (Ca)	282.0±0.19
5	Copper (Cu)	180.6±0.20
6	Magnesium (Mg)	130.0±0.24
7	Manganese (Mn)	65.9±0.26
8	Sodium (Na)	26.1±0.15
9	Chromium (Cr)	AB
10	Lead (Pb)	AB
11	Cadmium (Cd)	AB

Mean ± Standard deviation of three replications

AB = Absent

From the results in Table 2, eight essential minerals of interest were present at various concentrations. Three heavy metals assayed were not detected. The abundance of the available minerals is in the order:

$$Fe > K > Zn > Ca > Cu > Mg > Mn > Na$$

Iron composition was the highest in all the investigated minerals. Iron is a major component of haemoglobin and an essential element for blood production. It also supports

the immune system that fights diseases and infections (Megan, 2018). Iron composition of 2754.0 mg/100g was significantly higher than those obtained by some other researchers in Nigeria. The values obtained by Onajah and Emurotu, 2017 in Kogi State Nigeria and Okareh *et al.*, 2015 in Oyo State Nigeria were 406.0 mg/100g and 14.0 mg/100g respectively. High amount of potassium was also recorded. Diets with higher potassium to sodium ratio

have been shown to reduce blood pressure and prevent health-threatening ailments such as hypertension and arteriosclerosis while diets with higher Na to K ratio have been linked to instances of hypertension (Saupi *et al.*, 2009;

4.0.CONCLUSION

This research work has provided information on the nutritional importance, medicinal and mineral composition of a mature plantain fruit from Benin City, Nigeria. It was found to contain significantly high amount of Iron when compared with results from other workers. The

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presence of sufficient level of Iron and other mineral elements in the substrate indicates its nutritional potential and its reliability in fighting malnutrition and correcting nutritional disorders among people living in Nigeria and the world at large.

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